

Supplementary File 1: Morphological characters and states

If note stated otherwise pictures by Tamara Spasojevic or Alexandra Viertler

- ➔ Measurements in mm. (for ratios the measurement unit does not matter)
- ➔ If not stated otherwise, **female** species should be coded.

Green characters indicate it is from Klopstein & Spasojevic 2019 and Meier et al. 2022, character might be rephrased, but stayed the same with same states.

Blue characters were recoded from Klopstein & Spasojevic 2019, states were removed, added or newly interpreted.

Purple characters are new.

Head

MANDIBLES

[Default: Left mandible if possible]

#####

#1. Mandibles, tapering (base width relative to apex width) [ordered]:

- (0) weakly or parallel, apex width is at least 0.7x base width;
- (1) strongly tapered, apex width is 0.6-0.5x base width;
- (2) very strongly tapered, apex width is <0.4x base width.

[Apex width is measured at the base of the teeth]

(0) *Tryphon* sp.

(1) *Epitheronia* sp.

(2) *Orthopelma mediator*

#2. Mandibles, length relative to base width [ordered]:

- (0) length at least 3x base width;
- (1) length around 2-2.8x base width;
- (2) length equal or around 1.5x base width.

[Width at base is measured perpendicular to axis of mandible, thus ignoring the ventrobasally angle]

#3. Mandibles, **teeth, number** per mandible [ordered]:

- (0) unidentate (also when mandible only a “flap”, like in *Hybrizon*);
- (1) bidentate (includes twisted mandibles, when second tooth is present on the inside but not visible);
- (2) tridentate (upper tooth subdivided).

#4. Mandibles, teeth, tip shape:

- (0) strongly or slightly pointed to **evenly rounded**;
- (1) at least one tooth abruptly broken (**chisel-shaped**) (e.g. some Xoridinae);
- (2) weakly sclerotized - reduced to a **flap** (*Hybrizon*).

(0) *Cremastus* sp.

(1) *Rhyssa persuasoria*

(2) *Hybrizon buccatus*

#5. Mandibles, teeth, length of upper tooth compared with lower tooth [ordered]:

NA if unidentate

- (0) **conspicuously longer**, upper tooth around 2x length of lower tooth;
- (1) **subequal** to the lower;
- (2) distinctly **shorter** than lower tooth, about 0.6–0.7x its length;
- (3) **very small**, <0.4 length of lower.

[Measurements: start on base of both teeth to both longest points]

#6. Mandibles, teeth, width of upper tooth relative to lower tooth [ordered]:

NA if unidentate

- (0) **more slender**;
- (1) **similar to or very slightly broader**;
- (2) conspicuously **broad**er, lower might even be absent.

(0) Unidentified species

(1) *Tryphon* sp.

(2) Phaogenini sp.

#7. Mandibles, amount of twist around longitudinal axis [ordered]:

- (0) **not twisted** (Fig. 27);
- (1) **weakly twisted** about 20–40° (Fig. 26), sometimes lower tooth being shifted somewhat inwards compared to upper;
- (2) **twisted about 90°** so the inner tooth is not visible when mandibles closed (Fig. 32).

(0) *Lathrolestes orbitalis*

(2) *Proeliator proprius*

#8. Mandibles, **curvature (bending)** on longitudinal axis from clypeus border to mandible tip [ordered]:

Measure only when closed, otherwise estimate.

- (0) more or less straight ($<10^\circ$ from clypeus to tooth tip);
- (1) slightly bent ($\sim 20^\circ$ - 40°);
- (2) strongly bent ($>60^\circ$).

(1) *Anomalon* sp.

#9. Mandibles, dorsal surface, **chaetotaxy**:

- (0) with a cluster of stout long setae in a pit on ventral side;
- (1) with sparse scattered pubescence, sometimes glabrous;
- (2) with a diagonal line of hairs starting where the pit usually is and going down and towards the tip (see *Ophion*).

(2) *Leptophion* sp.

#10. Mandibles, apical 0.7 of length, **surface sculpture**:

- (0) more or less **punctate** or slightly rugulose (also due to hair);
- (1) strongly **striate**;
- (2) all **smooth** (sparse setae?) (some Orthocentrinae, Diplazontinae).

(0) *Euryophion* sp.

(1) *Tryphon* sp.

#####

MALAR SPACE

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#11. Malar space, **modification** [ordered]:

- (0) **without** any structure or with an incomplete sculptured band;
- (1) with a **sculptured band** in the place where the sulcus/impression would be, band extending over entire length;
- (2) with a **deep subocular sulcus/impression**.

(1) *Proelictor proprius*

(2) *Orthopelma mediator*

#12. Malar space, **length** relative to mandible width at base [ordered]:

- (0) **very short**, lower margin of eye almost touching base of mandible, at most 0.2 x base of mandible;
- (1) **short to moderately long**, 0.2– 0.8x basal mandibular width;
- (2) **long**, 1-1.5 x basal mandibular width;
- (3) **very long**, more than 1.8x basal mandibular width.

(0) *Leptophion* sp.

(1) *Pseudorhyssa nigricronis*

(2) *Spudaeus scaper*

(3) *Orthocentrus* sp.

PALPS
#####

#13. Maxillary palp, **number of segments** [ordered]:

- (0) five;
- (1) four;
- (2) three.

#14. Labial palp, **number of segments**:

- (0) four;
- (1) three.

LABRUM
#####

#15 Labiomaxillary complex, **modification**:

- (0) unspecialized;
- (1) elongated glossa (labium) and galeae (maxilla), with glossa concealed by galeae for most of its length;
- (2) elongated glossa (labium) and galeae (maxilla), with glossa reaching to fore coxae and exposed for most of its length (image to the right: *Lapton femoralis*).

#16. Labrum, **visibility**:

- (0) mostly **concealed** below clypeus, at most narrowly visible;
- (1) clearly **exposed** below clypeus.

#####

CLYPEUS

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#17. Clypeus, lateral view, **shape**:

- (0) **flat to slightly convex**, in the same plane as the lower face;
- (1) **slightly convex basally**, then **slightly concave apically**, so in median longitudinal section it would be slightly sinuous (e.g., *Ephialtini*, Fig. 44*);
- (2) **strongly convex basally** and remainder **protruding** from the face, **beak-like** (cf. *Helictes*-group in Orthocentrinae);
- (3) **strongly convex all the way**, an overall **roundish** shape (cf. *Ophion*, *Xestopelta*);
- (4) **strongly and evenly protruding from the base to the middle**, then **abruptly broken** with apical part almost completely horizontal, thus triangular in profile (many Ctenopelmatinae);
- (5) **flat basal part**, **apical part protruding**, so clypeus overall looks **slightly concave** (cf. *Heteropelma*);
- (6) **convex basally and apically**, but **central part concave** (cf. *Tryphon obtusator*);

(7) strongly convex dorsally and strongly concave ventrally (like a hawk's beak or a human nose - *Oedemopsis* and *Zagryphus* state.

#18. Clypeus, front view, **dimension** [ordered]:

Ratio: Write down **widest width of clypeus** (from mandible base to mandible base) / **longest length** (mostly measured in centre, if clypeal sulcus not there, measure from tentorial pits to clypeal apex).

Width / length

#19. Clypeus, **transverse division** (not clypeal sulcus):

- (0) absent;
- (1) present (photo to the right)

#20. Clypeus, transverse division, **size of apical part** compared with basal part:

- NA no division
- (0) **smaller** and **similarly sclerotised** as basal part (*Xanthopimpla*, *Lissopimpla*, *Hellwigia*);
- (1) **larger** and **less** or **similarly sclerotized** than basal part (some *Labeninae* and *Xoridinae*);
- (2) **with both parts equally sclerotised** (in tiny Cretaceous ichneumonid).

(0) *Hellwigia obscura*

(1) *Xorides praecatorius*

(2) Cretaceous fossil 3311/856b

#21. Clypeus, basal versus apical part, **abrupt change** in colour:

- (0) absent, no change or continuous change;
- (1) present, divided into two parts by structure (e.g., Banchinae)

#22. Clypeus, apical **margin, shape**:

- (0) evenly convex;
- (1) evenly concave;
- (2) bilobed;
- (3) trilobed;
- (4) truncate;
- (5) median angulation, beak-like (apical margin forming a broad triangular tooth).

(0) *Poecilocryptus* sp.

(1) *Labium* sp.

(2) *Diplazon* sp.

(3) *Trogus lutorius*

(4)

(5) *Sphinctus* sp.

#23. Clypeus, **apical margin, modification**:

- (0) rather **large central** denticle, just above apical margin;
- (1) with **two lateral tooth-like protrusions** (e.g. *Heteropelma*);
- (2) one or two **small round tubercles, centred**;
- (3) **central enlarged and rather wide tubercle(s)** (some *Rhyssa* sp.);

- (4) **many median tubercle-like structures** spreading along the margin (many Ctenopelmatinae);
- (5) with **additional sulcus** (double margin) (*Arotes moiwanus*);
- (6) **two lobes on the lateral outer corner**, seems below truncate apical margin;
- (7) with an **indentation** in the center.

(0)

(1) *Heteropelma* sp.

(2)

(3) *Rhyssa amoena*

(4) Ctenopelmatinae sp.

(5) *Arotes moiwanus*

(6)

#24. Clypeus, apical margin, **vestiture**:

- (0) **small, scattered setae** or lacking setae;
- (1) **regularly spaced**, parallel, strong setae (e.g. *Hercus*);
- (2) extremely **strong, spike-like setae**;
- (3) whole clypeus extremely densely covered in setae (*Glypta*, *Lissonota*).

(1) *Exenterus amictorius*

(2) *Perilissus* sp.

#25. Clypeus, apical margin, **compression** to thin margin:

- (0) absent (not compressed, not differentiated);
- (1) compressed, but not completely (e.g., only on centre, but laterally not compressed);
- (2) compressed, complete.

(1) *Anomalon cruentatum*

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FACE

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#26. Face, division by **clypeal sulcus**:

- (0) absent;
- (1) present, weakly impressed;
- (2) present, strongly impressed.

#27. Face, laterally, from antennal sockets to clypeal sulcus, shape:

- (0) flat to **slightly convex**, with weak median swelling;
- (1) apically **flat**, strongly protruding after middle;
- (2) **strongly protruding** (cf. *Strongylopsys*), the lower part in profile more or less straight or at most slightly convex (cf. *Orthocentrus*-group);
- (3) **strongly inflated**, very convex in profile (*Hypsicera* & *Exochus* in Metopiinae);
- (4) lower and upper face **convex or flat but impression in the middle**, looks like it has an upper bump;
- (5) shaped like a **shield** (cf. *Metopius*).

(0) *Cryptinae* sp.

(2) *Stenomacrus*

(3) *Exochus gravipes*

(4) *Ischnus inquisitorius*

(5) *Metopius* sp.

#28. Face, front view, dorsal end, **process** between antennal sockets:

- (0) absent;
- (1) present.

#29. Face, front view, dorsal end, **process** between antennal sockets, **type**:
NA if absent

- (0) with **triangular process**, mostly extends between or over the base of the antennae (cf. most Metopiinae);
- (1) with **concave groove**;
- (2) with a small **median horn**.
- (3) with transverse carina below antennal grooves, medially dipped or straight.

(0) *Metopius* sp.

(1) *Ctenopelmatinae* sp.

(2) *Sphinctus serotinus*

(3) *Mesochorus gemellus*

#30. Face, tentorial pits, **size** [ordered]:

- (0) very **small**, indistinct;
- (1) **middle size**, length between 1/3 and 1/2 of the breadth of the first flagellomere;
- (2) **large**, longer than 1/2 of the breadth of the first flagellomere, sometimes with strong depression around it.

#31. Face, front view, dimension, width relative to height [ordered]:

Face height (c) / head width (a)

[Measuring: **length of face (c)** (antennal socket to tentorial pit) / **width of head (a)**, at widest point of eye]

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EYES

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#32. Eyes, iridescence:

- (0) absent;
- (1) iridescent (Figure, *Meloboris alternans*).

#33. Eyes, inner margin, opposite antennal sockets, **invagination** [ordered]:

- (0) **straight;**
- (1) **weakly concave;**
- (2) with a **deep, more or less V-shaped** invagination (~0.5x width of 1st flagellomere);
- (3) with a **very deep, U-shaped** invagination (>1x width of 1st flagellomere).

(0) Cremastinae (1) *Clistopyga inciator* (2) *Leptophion* sp. (3) *Hellwigia obscura*

#34. Eyes, inner margins, front view, convergence:

[Measurements: shortest distance to largest distance between eyes]

- (0) 1-0.6 (eyes more or less parallel);
- (1) <0.6 (eyes strongly converging ventrally).

(0) (1) *Chriodes* sp.

#35. Eyes, height, lateral view, relative to head height (eye height/head length) [ordered]:

[Measuring: a) maximal eye height, b) maximal head height, from base of mandible to vertex]

#36. Eye, **width**, front view (width relative to head width) [ordered]:

[Measuring: **a**) **width of head**, at widest point of eye, **b**) **eye width**, same location]

#37. Eyes, surface hair:

- (0) **without** or inconspicuous **pubescence**;
- (1) **with** long conspicuous **pubescence** (cf. *Collyria trichophtalama*).

#38. Frons, **deep impressions** that accommodate scape: (from Meier et al. 2022)

- (0) absent, or weakly impressed;
- (1) present, strongly impressed (e.g. Townesitinae).

#39. Frons, between antennal sockets and median ocellus, **modification**:

- (0) absent or with low, inconspicuous carinae;
- (1) present.

#40. Frons, dorsal view, **modification** btw. antennal sockets and median ocellus, **type**:

NA if absent

- (0) **strongly raised keel** between antennae, reaching antenna or posteriorly (Metopiinae);
- (1) two low, parallel ridges from inner side of antennal scrobes towards middle ocellus;
- (2) low **longitudinal ridge** that might expand into a lobe at level of antennal sockets and reaching at least to ventral margin of antennal sockets (Acaenitinae);
- (3) **raised keel only between antenna that continues as a low ridge towards lower face** (the dorsal part same shape as in state 0);
- (4) **strong impression between toruli** and behind each toruli on the side closer to eyes, the central impression separated from the side ones by oblique ridges;
- (5) with a **horn**, which can be hollowed from above.

(6) two **prominent lobes** behind antennal sockets (Rogichneumon).

(0) *Metopius* sp.

(1) *Apophua evanescens*

(2) Acanitinae sp.

(3) *Heteropelma amictum*

(4) *Buathra laborator*

(5) *Ischnoceros rusticus* (6) *Rogichneumon braconidicus*

#41. Head, lateral ocelli, **distance to eye margin** relative to diameter of lateral ocelli
[ordered]

- (0) **distinctly shorter;**
- (1) about **same length** (+/- 10%);
- (2) **slightly longer**, 1.2-1.9x as long;
- (3) **distinctly longer**, at least 2x as long.

(0)

(1)

(2)

(3) *Alomya debellator*

#42. Head, ocelli, **stemmaticum** (raised triangular area):

- (0) not raised;
- (1) raised (photo on the right).

#43. Head, frontal orbit, colour, female:

- (0) **concolourous** with head colour;
- (1) with colour markings, different from head ground colour.

(1)

(1)

#44. Head size, dorsal view, **width** compared with mesosoma width [ordered]:

[Estimate: widest point of head width (including the eyes) and widest mesoscutum width]

- (0) head width distinctly smaller (<0.9x);
- (1) head width similar (0.9-1.1x)
- (2) head width larger (>1.1)

(1) *Triclistus* sp.

(2) Cretaceous fossil undescribed ("Knirps")

#45. Head, gena (area behind eyes), **sculpture:**

- (0) **smooth**, punctured, or shagreened;
- (1) with numerous **denticules**.

#####

BACK OF THE HEAD

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#46. Head, posterior side, **occipital carina**, upper end, **form:**

- (0) more or less **complete**, dorsally evenly convex or slightly flattened, normally raised (Figs 38, 39);
- (1) **broadly absent dorsally**, but ventrally present (Fig. 37*);
- (2) entirely **absent**;
- (3) more or less complete, dorsally evenly convex, flange-like;
- (4) more or less complete, dorsally strongly dipped (Fig. 36*), weakly raised, sometimes very weak or obsolescent near midline, but then with upper end of lateral portion curved downwards.
- (5) invaginated.

(0) (Gauld, 2002)

(1) (Gauld, 2002)

(4) (Gauld, 2002)

(5) *Dyspetes* sp.

#47. Head, lateral view, **vertex:**

- (0) moderately long, weakly and **evenly rounded** down to occipital carina;
- (1) **steeply declivous** behind ocelli but surface **flat or slightly convex**;
- (2) **long and convex**, usually with occipital carina rather low on head (many Polysphinctini);
- (3) precipitously **declivous** behind posterior ocelli, **concave** (eg. some Metopiinae);
- (4) **raised or horizontal**, then abruptly declivous behind occipital carina;
- (5) like the state (1) but **occipital carina very low on head**;
- (6) **very short**, distance between lateral ocelli and occipital carinae less than the diameter of the ocelli (cf. Anomaloninae);
- (7) **horizontal** to occipital carina and **weakly convex** (cf. Allomya).

(3) *Hypsicera femoralis*

(5) *Colpotrochia cincta*

(6) *Therion circumflexum*

(7) *Allomya debellator*

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ANTENNA

#48. Antenna, ratio of antenna and fore wing length [ordered]:

Antenna length measured including scapus and pedicel. Fore wing length measured from the wing base to the most distal point.

#49. Antenna, **number of flagellomeres** [ordered]:

Count flagellomeres.

#50. Antenna, **thickness**:

- (0) more or less of **even** thickness;
- (1) **evenly tapering** towards base, **broadest flagellomeres close to the antennal tip**;
- (2) abruptly **enlarged close to apex (club-like)**, including only a handful of segments;
- (3) tapering towards apex, last segments **conspicuously narrower** than basal ones;
- (4) broadest in the middle, tapering from there towards base and apex (cf. *Euceros*).

(1) *Pherombus*

(3) Goedartiini

(4) *Euceros* sp. (also in females sometimes noticeable)

#51. Antennae, apical flagellomere **modification, female** [associated with echolocation]:

- (0) absent;
- (1) present.

#52. Antennae, apical flagellomere, **type of modification, female**:

- NA if absent;
- (0) with some **thickened setae**;
- (1) with **cluster** of modified setae, that appear **rod-like**;
- (2) dense cluster of thickened and truncate structures forming a patch, no fusion of the structures, fused in the middle, or forming a flat surface (e.g. Labeninae);
- (3) **apex of flagellomere truncated** to leave a flat surface without sensillae or hairs (cf. *Echthrus*);
- (4) with **two rows of conspicuously modified setae** along entire length of apical flagellomere (cf. *Xorides*).

#53. Antenna, front view, **pedicle, length** relative to **scape**:

- (0) clearly **smaller than scape**, not inflated, only of slightly greater diameter than 1st flagellomere;
- (1) **strongly inflated**, almost as broad as scape and distinctly broader than 1st flagellomere.

#54. Antenna, lateral view, **pedicle, width** relative to **scape**:

- (0) conspicuously **shortened**, so it is laterally no longer than pedicel and shorter than wide (cf. *Metopius*);
- (1) **1-1.5 times longer than wide**, truncation oblique;
- (2) **elongate-cylindrical**, >1.8x as long as wide, truncation at about 60-90° to longitudinal axis (cf. *Orthocentrus* group);

(0) *Metopius* sp.

(1) *Exenterus amictorius*

(2) *Orthocentrus* sp.

#55. Antenna, front view, scape, truncation:

- (0) horizontal more or less;
- (1) slightly truncated;
- (2) strongly truncated, at least to half-length of scape or more.

#56. Antenna, scape, extended **membranous area**:

- (0) absent;
- (1) dorsally present (cf. *Megastylus*);
- (2) ventrally present, with dorsal side of scape inflexed under the ventral side (Picture: *Xanthopimpla* sp.).

57. Antenna, **1st** flagellomere, dimension:

[Measurement: Longest length & apical width]

58. Antenna, 5th **last** flagellomere, dimension:

Ratio: Measure 5th last segment dimension, length / apical width.

#59. Antenna, flagellum, basal or central flagellomeres, **tyloids**, male:

- (0) absent;
- (1) present.

#60. Antenna, flagellum, basal or central flagellomeres, **tyloid shape**, male:

- NA if absent
- (0) **elliptical** (cf. *Sussaba cognata*);
- (1) **linear** (cf. *Promethes sulcator*);
- (2) **concave** (Cylloceriinae);
- (3) raised, **tooth-like** (cf. *Helcostizus restaurator*).

#61. Antenna, flagellum, colour:

- (0) **without** a median white band;
- (1) with a **median** (also in last 3/4) white band;
- (2) with a **basal** white band (e.g. *Cymodusa*).

#####

Mesosoma

Pronotum

#62. Pronotum, lateral view, **dimension**:

- (0) **short and high**, <0.6 times as long as deep ;
- (1) **moderately long**, 0.8–1.0 times as long as deep;
- (2) **long**, >1.1 times as long as deep.

Measurement: height from tegula to ventral end; length is from anterior collar in 90° to middle of pronotum

(0) *Echthromorpha* sp.

(1) *Gelis areoator*

(2) *Xoridinae* sp.

#63. Pronotum, **epomia**:

- (0) **complete**, forming a weak ridge shaped like a figure 7 or **reduced** with only upper part present;
- (1) entirely **absent** (Figs 49, 51);
- (2) with **lower part long**, extending almost till the ventral margin of the pronotum, while pronotum clearly raised below the epomia;
- (3) with lower part long and **strongly raised** as a flange;
- (4) with epomia very **strong and expanded** dorsally into a **tooth**;
- (5) as (2) but pronotum **not raised below the epomia**, instead the anterior margin protruding into a **tooth**.

(0) *Clistopyga incitator*

(4) *Xorides* sp.

(5) *Heteropelma amictum*

#64. Pronotum, upper hind corner, between mesopleuron, mesoscutum and tegula, **sclerite**:

- (0) with a **tiny sclerite** present between hind corner of pronotum, mesopleuron and tegula, thus causing the pronotum to bow out a little around this sclerite;
- (1) pronotum partially overgrowing this sclerite, but sclerite **partially visible** (e.g. Banchinae, Ctenopelmatinae);
- (2) pronotum **completely overgrowing** this sclerite (cf. Metopiinae).

(1) Euryproctini (2) *Exochus gravipes*

#65. Propleuron, posterior side, hind corner, lateroventral posteriorly-projecting **lobe**:

- (0) **absent**;
- (1) **present** (Picture: *Dusona terebrator*).

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Mesoscutum

#66. Mesoscutum, **sculpture**:

- (0) finely **punctate**;
- (1) **smooth** and impunctate;
- (2) very **coarsely punctate**, with punctures separated inter se by about their own diameter;
- (3) **coarsely and closely punctate**, the punctures more or less contiguous;
- (4) evenly **shagreened** and matt;
- (5) with sharp **transverse rugae**;
- (6) with **strong punctures** and **longitudinal striae** formed of confluent punctures (cf. *Armadillocryptus*);
- (7) with **coarse rugae** forming a **net-like pattern**, at least on median part.

(1) *Absyrtus vicinator*

(3) *Mansa* sp.

(4) *Rossemia longithorax*

(5) *Rhyssa* sp.

#67. Mesoscutum, **pubescence:**

- (0) **evenly pubescent;**
- (1) **glabrous**, at most with a **few setae around front or position of notauli**, these hairs **short;**
- (2) **glabrous**, but with a **few very long setae** along front and position of notauli, these hairs as long as diameter of flagellomere 1
- (3) **middle evenly pubescent**, laterally more **glabrous**.

#68. Mesoscutum, near base of notaulus, **modification:**

- (0) absent:
- (1) present.

#69. Mesoscutum, near base of notaulus, **modification, type:**

- NA if no modification
- (0) with a **thickening** or crest at the base of notauli (cf. *Lissopimpla*, *Xanthopimpla*);
- (1) with a **short carina** directly in front of and parallel to notaulus (cf. some Orthocentrinae);
- (2) with **strong protrusion** of mesoscutum between notauli into paired lobes;
- (3) with **pronotal margin** laterally **swollen**;
- (4) with a **paired crest** at the anterior dorso-lateral part of mesoscutum (cf. *Acrodactyla degener*);

(0) *Xanthopimpla varimaculata* (#2448)

#70. Mesoscutum, lateral view, slope of **median lobe** [ordered]:

(0) evenly **rounded**, not strongly protruding;

(1) **rounded**, but **horizontally risen** after vertical part of pronotum, sometimes overhanging;

(2) clearly **overhanging** pronotum, also as triangular extension over pronotum.

(0) *Rasnichneumon gracilis*

(1) *Tryphon* sp.

(2) *Rhyssa persuasoria*

(2) *Xanthopimpla*

(2) *Jezarotes tamanukii*

#71. Mesoscutum, lateral view, anterior extension:

- (0) absent;
- (1) present (e.g. *Rasnichneumon alexandri*, Photo)

#72. Mesoscutum, lateral carina, **margin**:

- (0) **complete** to anterior end of scutellum;
- (1) **evanescent**, not reaching the scutellum.

(0) *Rosemia* sp.

#73. Mesoscutum, lateral carina, posteriorly, **height**:

- (0) normal carina, not or only barely broader than it is anteriorly;
- (1) **strongly broadened**, at least twice as wide as it is anteriorly.

(1) *Metopius* sp.

#74. Mesoscutum, notaulus, **strength** [ordered]:

- (0) **not impressed**;
- (1) **shallow** or vestigial;
- (2) **deeply impressed**, at least anteriorly.

#75. Mesoscutum, notaulus, **length**:

- NA if absent
- (0) present only on the **frontal vertical** part of mesoscutum;

- (1) extending to about **half length** of mesoscutum;
- (2) extending **posteriorly** past centre.

#76. Mesoscutum, notaulus, **shape**:

NA if absent

- 0) more or less **parallel (or converging and then parallel)**;
- 1) **converging**, not joining other notaulus;
- 2) **strongly converging**, joining either the other notaulus or a sunken, medial area.

(0) *Pseudorhyssa* sp.

(2) *Xorides* sp.

#####

Scutellum

#77. Scutellum, **lateral longitudinal carinae**:

- (0) **absent** or only discernible on extreme anterior end;
- (1) more or less complete to centre or beyond, but not reaching posterior margin;
- (2) **complete** to posterior margin;
- (3) **complete AND** expanded posteriorly into **two acute teeth** (cf. *Metopius*).

(2) *Chorinaeus cristator*

(3) *Metopius*

#78. Scutellum, lateral view, **shape**:

- (0) more or less **flat**;
- (1) a **bit convex**;

- (2) **pyramidal, strongly convex**, sometimes even drawn into a point between base and middle of scutellum (more triangular pyramid), **posterior surface long**, evenly **declivous**;
- (3) **strongly convex** in profile, **posterior surface convex**, rather **short** (e.g. *Phorotrophus*);
- (4) **pyramidal**, but with acute highest point almost at the end, after steeply declivous (*Astiphromma dorsale* group);
- (5) as state 2, but with carinae along the posterior slope (and at lower front corners - triangular pyramid);
- (6) strongly pyramidal, but also with the whole shape (*Opheltes*);
- (7) bit convex with posterior part raised (*Tymmophorus*).

(1) Acanitinae sp.

#79. Metanotum (=postscutellum), lateral, view, **shape**:

- (0) **flat to evenly convex**;
- (1) **conspicuously short**, sharply rounded and strongly declivous posteriorly (cf. *Camptotypus*);
- (2) **triangular** and pointed (cf. some Orthocentrinae);
- (3) nearly absent, **only a slightly thickened carina** in its place (cf. *Diaparsis*);
- (4) **long** and flat, with **two low longitudinal carinae** and small swelling posteriorly.

#80. Metanotum (=postscutellum), **modification**:

- (0) absent
- (1) present in form of a posterolateral triangle.

(1) *Stilpnus gagates*

#81. Scutellum, metanotum/metapleuron, length:

- 0) **short**, so that the constriction between metanotum and propodeum is very close after the postscutellum;
- 1) **elongate**, so that the constriction is clearly removed from the postscutellum, by about 0.2-0.3x the length of the propodeum (Figure: *Scutellator macrommatus* Kasparyan & Humala, 1995)

#####

Mesopleuron

#82. Mesopleuron, **centrally**:

- (0) **rather flat or weakly convex**, at most with a weak diagonal impression delineating a convex area posterodorsally;
- (1) with a **diagonal impression** reaching upper third of mesopleuron **to mesopleural sulcus**;
- (2) very **strongly convex** so that the body is much wider when viewed from above at height of mesopleuron than further back at the mesepimeron (some Metopiinae);
- (3) **horizontal**, or more or less diagonal, groove (often carinated) from lower half of hind margin of pronotum to posterior margin of mesopleuron, on **height of mid coxa** (Tersilochinae).

(1) *Temelucha* sp.

(2) *Chorinaeus cristator*

#83. Mesopleuron, **epicnemial carina**:

- (0) absent (e.g. Poemeninae);
- (1) present.

#84. Mesopleuron, **epicnemial carina**:

- NA if absent
- (0) not curving anteriorly, **vertical to around mid-height** of pronotum;
- (1) **curving to anterior end** of mesopleuron at around the mid-height of the pronotum;
- (2) **extending all the way** to subtegular ridge;
- (3) **present ventrally only** (not extending dorsally to ventral edge of pronotum);
- (4) **present only laterally**.

(0) *Phytodietus polyzonas*

(2) *Exochus* sp.

#85. Mesopleuron, **mesopleural furrow**:

- (0) weakly or strongly **angled** opposite mesepisternal scrobe, usually **with a shallow horizontal impression** extending from this angulation to the scrobe (Fig. 53);
- (1) more or less **straight** with a **shallow horizontal impression** extending from this angulation to the scrobe;
- (2) more or less **straight** with **isolate punctate** instead of the horizontal impression;
- (3) more or less **straight** straight, but with a diagonally-upward-pointing groove, delineating the speculum, which is short, higher than long (e.g. *Banchus*);
- (4) with a **sinusoid portion** in lower third, then an angle of $\sim 60^\circ$ at lower 0.4, then again with a weak angle around height of scrobe (e.g. *Tryphon obtusator*).

(0) *Tromatobia* sp.

(1) *Pimpla turionellae*

(4) *Tryphon* sp.

#86. Mesopleuron, ventrally (mesosternum), behind fore coxae:

- (0) simply **transverse**;
- (1) produced forwards in a **broad blunt angulation** (anterior transverse carina produced forward);
- (2) produced forwards in a **narrow blunt angulation**, with mesosternum protruding in the middle forming a vertical ridge;
- (3) produced forward into a **large lobe**;
- (4) with a **pointed tubercle** in the middle of mesosternum.

#87. Mesopleuron, ventrally, **posterior transverse carina** of mesosternum:

- (0) **completely absent**;
- (1) **absent in front of the middle coxae**, present otherwise (e.g. *Therion*);
- (2) **complete** (e.g. *Dusona*);
- (3) **short** and present only in the middle in-between the two mid coxae;
- (4) clearly **present laterally**, but absent in front of the mid coxa, in between coxae absent/fused with anterior transverse carina;
- (5) **absent laterally** but **present as extended flanges** in **front of the mid coxae and in between**;
- (6) **absent laterally** but **present as extended flanges** in **front of the mid coxae**, otherwise normal carinae between middle coxa.

#88. Mesopleuron, laterally, **sternaulus**:

- (0) absent or present less than 0.7x length of mesopleuron;
- (1) present, greater than or equal to 0.7x length of mesopleuron.

#89. Mesopleuron, laterally, posterior **ending of sternaulus**:

- NA if absent
- (0) ending **below or at** level of mid coxa (many Cryptinae);
- (1) ending **above** level of mid coxa (many Phygadeuontinae).

(0) *Mesostenus* sp.

(1) *Gelis areator*

#####

Metapleuron

#90. Metapleuron, **dimensions**:

- (0) clearly **higher than long** (cf. Diplazontinae);
- (1) about **as long as wide**;
- (2) **1.7-2x as long as wide**.

[Measurement: **Highest height** (from the ventral edge of metapleuron, but not including metapleural carina, to propodeal carina) and **longest length** (from the end of propodeal groove to the end of metapleuron)]

(0) *Diplazon* sp.

(1)

(2) *Nonnus* sp.

#91. Metapleuron, **submetapleural carina**:

- (0) **complete**(Fig xx *Pimpla*);

- (1) **anteriorly present**, posteriorly not complete or absent;
- (2) completely **absent**.

#92. Metapleuron, submetapleural carina, **anterior section**:

- (0) anterior section **unmodified**;
- (1) anterior section **slightly** broadened;
- (2) anterior section **abruptly** broadened into a lobe;
- (3) broadened on the **whole** length.

#93. Metapleuron, **juxacoxal carina**, presence:

- (0) mostly **absent** (only with indications at beginning and/or end);
- (1) partially **reduced** or weak;
- (2) present as **distinct carina** on whole length.

#94. Metapleuron, **pleural carina**:

- (0) mostly **absent** (only with indications at beginning and/or end);
- (1) partially **reduced** or weak;
- (2) **present** as distinct carina on whole length.

#####

Propodeum

#95. Propodeum, **sculpture** :

- (0) **smooth** and shiny, without reticulation between carinae and at most with some weak punctures where hairs are inserted (Fig. 55*);
- (1) mostly covered by **reticulation** that obscures carinae;
- (2) with **distinct punctures**;
- (3) **rugulopunctate**;
- (4) with **weak punctures**, distance more than their diameter;
- (5) **evenly shagreened** and matt without distinct punctures;
- (6) with strong longitudinal **wavy pattern** between carinae (cf. *Armadillocryptus*);
- (7) with transverse **parallel rugae (or simply striate)** between carinae.

(0) Gauld et al. 2002

(1) *Therion circumflexum*

(2) (Gauld et al. 2002)

(7) *Lissopimpla excelsa* (Gauld et al. 2002)

#96. Propodeum, lateral view, **shape** [main part, until coxal cavity]:

- (0) from **rounded** to dorsally flattened, and with a posterior surface (Fig. 59);
- (1) evenly **declivous** (Fig. 60);
- (2) with petiolar area **deeply concave** to take in petioles (cf. Townesitinae, *Sinophorus*).

#97. Propodeum, posterior **protrusion** (after hind coxal cavity):

- (0) absent;
- (1) present (postero-medial part elongated behind the hind coxae into a process that carries the metasoma, this process about 1/3 to 2/3 as long as propodeum itself).

#98. Propodeum, posterior protrusion, **position relative to anterior height of propodeum**:

- NA if absent
- (0) **centred** on posterior margin (e.g. Pherombinae);

- (1) **ventrally** on posterior margin (e.g. Anomaloninae).

(0) *Pherombus antennalis*

(1) *Therion circumflexum*

#99. Propodeum, **dimension:**

- (0) **clearly shorter than high** (cf. Diplazontinae);
(1) about **as long as high** (Figs 61, 62) (but sometimes with postero-median part further elongated, cf. Heteropelma);
(2) **elongate**, distinctly longer than wide, cylindrical.

(0)

(1) *Gambrus* sp.

(2) *Lorio* sp.

#100. Propodeum, **longitudinal carinae, completeness:**

- (0) absent;
(1) **only lateromedian** longitudinal carinae present;
(2) **only lateral longitudinal** carinae present;
(3) **both lateromedian** and lateral longitudinal carinae present.
(4) anterior portion of median longitudinal carinae **fused**.

#101. Propodeum, **anterior transverse carina, completeness:**

- (0) complete (medially and sublaterally);
(1) median abscissa present, sublateral abscissae (= costulae) absent;
(2) median abscissa absent, sublateral abscissae present;
(3) completely absent.

#102. Propodeum, anterior transverse carina, **shape:**

NA if carina absent or incomplete so that angulation/curvature could not be scored

- (0) angled;
(1) forming more or less a smooth arc (Fig. xx *Ophion flavidus*).

#103. Propodeum, **posterior transverse carina, completeness:**

- (0) **complete** (medially and sublaterally);
(1) **medial abscissa present**, sublateral abscissae absent;

- (2) **median abscissa absent**, sublateral abscissae present (areolar area confluent with petiolar area);
- (3) completely absent/indistinguishable.

#104. Propodeum, **posterior transverse carina, shape:**

NA if carina absent or angulation uncertain

- (0) angled;
- (1) more or less a continuous arc.

#105. Propodeum, spiracle, **shape:**

[Measurements: relative to inner margin of spiracle]

- (0) **subcircular to oval**, < 2.0 times as long as wide (Fig. 59);
- (1) **elongated oval** >2.0 but less than 3.5 times as long as wide (Fig. 60);
- (2) **elongated elliptical** >3.5 times as long as wide (Fig. 63).

(2) *Coelichneumon biannulatus*

#106. Propodeum, spiracle, **distance from pleural carina** [ordered]:

- (0) separated from pleural carina by less than minimum diameter (Photo: *Pseudorhyssa* sp.);
- (1) separated from pleural carina by about minimum diameter of spiracle or more;
- (2) at least double minimum diameter distance from pleural carina.

#107. Propodeum, junction lateral longitudinal and posterior apical transverse carinae, **modification:**

- (0) absent;
- (1) present.

#108. Propodeum, junction lateral longitudinal and posterior apical transverse carinae, **modification, type:**

- NA if absent
- (0) with subconical apophyses (Figs 57, 63);

- (1) with posterior transverse carina elevated into a flange on points where lateral longitudinal carina would have joined (cf. *Buathra*);
- (2) with flanges (cf. *Opheltes*).

(0) (Gauld et al. 2002)

(0) (Gauld et al. 2002)

#109. Propodeum, postero-median surface, **modification:**

- NA if absent
- (0) with a strong **single median tubercle** (63);
- (1) with posterior transverse carina elevated into a flange that forms a shelf.

63

#110. Propodeum, posterior margin, **modification:**

- (0) absent, margin simple;
- (0) present, margin extended and covering anterior part of metasomal first tergite (*Xanthopimpla*).

#111. Propodeum, posteriorly, ventral view, **metacoxal cavity:**

- (0) dorsal margin is **above** lower margin of metasomal foramen magnum;
- (1) dorsal margin **on same height** of lower margin of metasomal foramen magnum;
- (2) dorsal margin is (**clearly**) **below** lower margin of metasomal foramen magnum.

(0) (Gauld & Wahl, 2000)

(2) (Gauld & Wahl, 2000)

#####

Legs

Fore legs

#112. Fore legs, tibia, **enlargement/inflation**:

- (0) absent;
- (1) present.

#113. Fore legs, tibia, **enlargement/inflation, location**:

- (0) only fore legs;
- (1) all legs.

#114. Fore legs, tibia, **spines** (not setae):

- (0) without spines, **smooth** (except normal pubescence);
- (1) with scattered **long** and **stronger spines**;
- (2) bearing **stout short conical spines** set in pits.

(1) *Mesostenus albinotatus*

(2) *Pseudorhyssa* sp.

#115. Fore legs, apex of tibia, **tooth**:

- (0) absent;
- (1) present, distinct tooth on dorsal margin.

(1) *Ctenopelmatinae* sp.

#116. Fore legs, 4th tarsomere, **dimension**:

- (0) clearly longer than wide;
- (1) very broad, as long as wide or wider than long (photo: *Exochus gravipes*).

#117. Fore legs, 5th tarsomere, **swelling**, female:

- (0) slender, of similar thickness to other tarsomeres;
- (1) exceptionally swollen;
- (2) very elongated (~3x length of 4th tarsomere) and bowed (e.g. *Hadrodactylus*);
- (3) very elongated (~3x length of 4th tarsomere), but not bowed (e.g. *Agriotypus*).

#118. Fore legs, **femur length** (incl. trochanter) compared with forewing length:

- (0) < 0.3x forewing;
- (1) > 0.3x forewing.

#119. Fore legs, **trochantellus, length** [ordered]:

Ratio: Length of femur / length of trochanter&trochantellus

#120. Fore and mid legs, **trochantellus, fusion**:

- (0) absent, clearly differentiated from femur;
- (1) present (Metopiinae).

#####

Mid legs

#121. Mid leg, tibia, **number of spurs**:

- (0) **two** spurs;
- (1) **one** spur (e.g. *Metopius*).

#122. Mid leg, tibia, spurs, inner spur, **relative length** to outer spur:

- (0) clearly **longer** than outer spur;
- (1) **equal** in length (+/- 10%);
- (2) clearly **shorter** than outer spur.

#123. Mid and hind leg, tibia, ventral view **apex**:

- (0) with common area of insertion for spurs and basitarsus;
- (1) with **sclerotized bridge** separating insertion areas (Cremastinae).

#####

Hind legs

#####

#124. Hind leg, coxa, **proportions [ordered]:**

Ratio: Longest length/widest width

#125. Hind leg, coxa, **modification:**

- (0) evenly rounded;
- (1) bluntly angled on ventrolateral edge (e.g. *Xanthopimpla*, *Lissopimpla*);
- (2) with a tooth on under side towards the apex (cf. *Phaeogenes*).

#126. Hind leg, coxa, **inner surface**, female:

- (0) simply convex;
- (1) with shallow groove;
- (2) with shallow groove bordered by sharp parallel carinae;
- (3) with furrow covered with grossulariform setae (Labeninae).

#127. Hind leg, femur, ventral, **modification:**

- (0) absent;
- (1) present, with a **blunt tooth**.

#128. Hind leg, femur, **dimensions [ordered]:**

Ratio: Femur length (longest length) / Femur width (widest width).

Trochanter and trochantellus should be omitted.

#129. Hind **tibia, length**, compared with hind femur [ordered]:

Ratio: Length tibia/length femur.

#130. Hind tibia, number of spurs:

- (0) **two** spurs;
- (1) **one** spur.

#131. Hind tibia, **inner spur**, relative length to outer spur:

- NA if single spur
- (0) clearly **longer** than outer spur;
- (1) **equal** in length;

- (2) clearly **shorter** than outer spur

#132. Hind tibia, **spines** (not setae):

- (0) without spines, smooth (except normal pubescence);
(1) with scattered spines (spines much slender compared to the state 2 spines, not very obvious among setae);
(2) bearing stout short conical spines (often a little darker than surrounding colour).

(2) *Hypsicera femoralis*

#133. Hind tibia, **colouration pattern**:

- (0) uniformly coloured (black, red, brown, orange, white, yellow);
(1) with apex darkened;
(2) with base darkened;
(3) with base AND apex darkened;
(4) dark-bright-dark banded;
(5) with a light base;
(6) with a light base AND light apex;
(7) longitudinally split: orange in posterior, brown in anterior half;
(8) longitudinally split: dark in posterior (outer), orange in anterior half (inner).

#134. Hind tibia, inner side of apex, **setae**:

- (0) only with a **few hairs** apically which are **very similar** as the hairs on the surface;
(1) present as a **fringe of parallel setae which are very similar** to main pubescence;
(2) present as a very **dense fringe of parallel bristle** which clearly differs from the main pubescence of the tibia AND from the fringe on the OUTER surface (many Orthocentrinae).

(1) *Colpotrochia cincta*

#135. Hind tibia, apical width, relative to central width of 1st tarsomere [ordered]:

Ratio: Apex width tibia (widest point) / width 1st tarsomere.

#136. Hind tarsus, 1st tarsomere, **dimension** [ordered]:

Write down the proportions: length / width

#137. Hind legs, 2nd to 4th tarsomere of female ventrally:

- (0) with pubescence that is similar to the dorsal pubescence;
- (1) with strong stout spines that are obviously thicker than the dorsal pubescence.

#138. Hind tarsus, 4th tarsomere, **apex**:

- (0) apically more or less **evenly truncated**;
- (1) **obliquely truncated**, so that inner side overhangs base of the fifth tarsomere.

#####

Claws

#####

#139. Tarsal claws, **dimension**, female:

- (0) normal sized (see Fig. X);
- (1) very elongated and slender (e.g. *Agriotypus*);
- (2) very enlarged and prominent (e.g. *Xanthopimpla*).

(0)

(2) *Epitheronia* sp.

#140. Tarsal claws, **modification**, female:

- (0) absent;
- (1) present.

#141 Tarsal claws, modification, **location**, female:

NA is absent.

- (0) all modified;
- (1) hind simple, others modified;
- (2) fore modified others simple.

#142. Tarsal claws, modification, **type**, female:

NA if claws simple

- (0) broad **basal lobe**;
- (1) additional **tooth** next to the tip of the claw;
- (2) claws **pectinate**, i.e., with a comb-like row of teeth starting near base and extending to middle or even to apex of claw;
- (3) basal tooth (e.g. Othopelmatinae).
- (4) with **bevelled apex** (e.g. *Poecilocryptus nigromaculatus*).

#143. Tarsal claws, pectination:

NA if absent

- (0) throughout;
- (1) not pectinate until apex.

#144. Hind claws, **orbicula** (sclerotized part between claws):

- (0) **short** and moderately broad, between 2.5 and 3.5 times as long as wide;
- (1) **very slender and bar-like**, >3.5 times as long as wide (Fig. 91);
- (2) **very short**, only about 2x as long as wide.;
- (3) **broad and expanded** anteriorly, almost as long as wide (see *Heteropelma*).

#145. Hind claws, **arolium** (membranous pad between claws):

- (0) of normal dimensions, not projecting beyond apex of claw;
- (1) enlarged, projecting conspicuously beyond apex of claw (Fig. 93).

(1) *Acrotaphus tibialis* (Gauld et al. 2002)

#146. Hind claws, inner side, **poison vesicle**:

[if uncertain code polymorphic state: (0,1,2)]

- (0) without any trace of a membranous poison vesicle;
- (1) with a small membranous vesicle on inside of apical tooth of male;
- (2) with a small membranous vesicle in male and female;

- (3) with a large membranous vesicle in both sexes.

#147. Hind claws, **spatulate bristle**:

- (0) **absent**;
- (1) present, long conspicuous spatulate bristle, the apex of which (at rest) is pressed against the pointed apex of the claw.

(1) *Neotheronia mellosa* (Gauld et al. 2002)

#####

Wings

Above, fore wing: Viertler et al. 2022
 Below, hind wing: Spasojevic et al. 2018

#148. Fore wing, **areolet**, vein **3rs-m**:

- (0) absent;
- (1) spectral ~ 100%;
- (2) 1 bulla;
- (3) 2 bullae;

(4) without bulla.

#149. Fore wing, **areolet, shape:**

- (0) **quadrate-oblique to triangular**, 2+3M longer than 4M, 2Rs more than 0.3x 3M (A)
- (1) **rombic**, all sides almost equal (B);
- (2) **pentagonal**, with +/- even sides (C);
- (3) as 0, but 2Rs less than 0.3x 3M (note if all obliterated) (D);
- (4) **widened pentagonal**, > 1.5 times as wide as deep (Labenopimplinae type, (E);
- (5) **pentagonal**, but with 3Rs very short (Fig. 116);
- (6) **strongly petiolate** (put <= one vein diameter into state 0 or 9) (G),
- (7) with **2Rs very long**, more than 2x 2+3M (H);
- (8) with 2Rs absent, thus **areolet open towards the inside**, (I);
- (9) quadrate-asymmetric, but not oblique: with 3M shorter than 4M, and 2Rs of similar length as 3M (usually rather big areolet, cf. many Metopiinae, J).

#150. Fore wing, **vein 2m-cu, presence:**

- (0) present;
- (1) indicated by angulation of 4Rs and/or 5M (come cretaceous fossils);
- (2) absent.

#151. Fore wing, **vein 2m-cu, number of bullae:**

- (0) with two bullae separated with only trace of the vein or with longer part of the vein;
- (1) with a single bulla;
- (2) entirely spectral.

#152. Fore wing, **vein 2m-cu, size of bullae** [ordered]:

Percentage of the vein that belongs to bullae (eg. when 1 bulla: 60, when 2 bullae: 20+20,)

#153. Fore wing, **vein 2m-cu, shape:**

- (0) straight;
- (1) more or less evenly bowed outwards;
- (2) anteriorly bowed outwards, posteriorly inwards, thus forming a zig-zag or at least sinuous curve;
- (3) bowed or angled inwards;
- (4) anteriorly straight or even bowed inwards, about posterior half bowed outwards, looks sinusoidal.

(3) *Lycorina*

(4) *Pedunculus*

#154. Fore wing, vein 2m-cu, position of bullae

- (0) rather anteriorly;
- (1) evenly distributed or centred;
- (2) rather posteriorly on vein.

#155. Fore wing, **discosubmarginal** cell (1M+1R1), pubescence:

- (0) uniformly hirsute;
- (1) with small to large glabrous area that may have free sclerites (cf. *Leptophion*).

#156. Fore wing, **discosubmarginal** cell (1M+1R1), **extension** beyond 2m-cu:

- (0) not extending;
- (1) extending.

#157. Fore wing, **vein 4Rs**, **shape**:

- (0) almost straight;
- (1) proximally arched;
- (2) distally arched;
- (3) clearly sinusoidal;
- (4) evenly arched towards 1R1;
- (5) evenly arched towards 2R1.

(1) *Eurylabus torvus*

#158. Fore wing, spurious vein on cell 3Cu paralleling wing margin, presence:

- (0) absent;
- (1) present.

#159. Fore wing, 1cu-a angle to 2Cu:

- (0) angle clearly smaller than 65°-70°;

(1) more or less in a right angle (more than 80°)
 #160. Fore wing, length of 4Cu relative to 5Cu [ordered]:
 Ratio of two measurements, measure along the vein:

#161. Fore wing, **ramulus** (remaining of the vein 1Rs+M), **length**:

- (0) absent;
- (1) present, at most as long as the width of the surrounding veins;
- (2) present, longer as the width of the surrounding veins (mostly reaching till half of the way to M).

#162. Fore wing, **vein 1cu-a (nervulus position)**:

- (0) meeting vein M+CU basal of M&RS by more than 1 vein width ("nervulus antefurkal");
- (1) at level of M&RS ("interstitial");
- (2) distal of M&RS by more than 1 vein width ("postfurkal");
- (3) extremely posterior so that vein 1Cu is more than 0.8x longer than the vein 2Cu (some Brachycyrtinae).

#163. Fore wing, **pterostigma, dimensions**:

write ratio (length/ height)

#164. Fore wing, ratio of pterostigma length to 1R1 (vein) length

Write ratio.

#165. Fore wing, marginal cell (2R1), dimensions:

Write ratio (longest length/widest width)

#166. Fore wing, **vein 5M**:

- (0) vein tubular through the whole length (not counting the last 10% of the vein), same colour as or slightly lighter than the colour of the surrounding veins;
- (1) vein partly spectral (not counting the last 10% of the vein);
- (2) vein through whole length spectral (+-);
- (3) absent.

#167. Fore wing, pterostigma, **location** of insertion for vein r-rs:

Ratio: Length of pterostigma until vein r-rs (1) / total length of pterostigma (2).

#168. Fore wing, ratio of 2Cu length to 1M+1Rs length [ordered]:

Write ratio.

#169. Fore wing, ratio of 2Cu length to r-rs length [ordered]:

Write ratio.

#170. Fore wing, ratio of 1M+1Rs to r-rs [ordered] (Meier et al. 2022)

Write ratio.

#171. Fore wing, ratio of 1cu-a to 1M+1Rs [ordered]:

Write ratio.

#172. Fore wing, 1m-cu&2Rs+M vein, shape:

- (0) straight;
- (1) arched around midlength;
- (2) angled around midlength;
- (3) with a rounded hump; [delete in the end]
- (4) distal bow, can be very strong;
- (5) strongly and evenly curved along entire length;
- (6) proximally strongly curved, then straight.

(6) *Sphinctus serotinus*

#173. Fore wing, dimension of cell 2Cu (measured by 2A to 1cu-a length) [ordered]:

Write ratio.

#174. Fore wing, **postnervulus**, location of the junction from vein 2Cu-a and 3Cu to vein 4Cu [ordered]:

- (0) 0-0.25,
- (1) 0.25-0.5,
- (2) 0.5-0.75,

(3) 0.75-1.

Note: If exactly in the middle, code: (1,2)

#175. Fore wing, fusion of C and R (costa and subcosta)

(0) fused or at least very close to each other, no membrane between visible (all crown group Ichneumonidae);

(1) some distance apart, with membranous area between (in stem groups only).

#####

Hind wings

#176. Hind wing, vein M+CU, shape:

(0) straight, except for short bow near base;

(1) curved distally;

(2) curved at round middle, more or less straight before and after;

(3) slightly curved on entire length.

#177. Hind wing, Vein M+Cu, completeness:

(0) complete;

(1) basal 0.6 spectral (Fig. xx Allophrys)

#178. Hind wing, 2nd abscissa of CU (2CU) / (2CU + cu-a) (nervellus), interception:

NA- inapplicable, nervellus not intercepted.

(0) 0-0.25;

(1) 0.25-0.5;

(2) 0.5-0.75;

(3) 0.75-1.

Note: If exactly in the middle, code: (1,2)

#179. Hind wing, last abscissa of RS (2RS), sclerotization:

(0) vein tubular through the whole length (not counting the last 10% of the vein), same colour as or slightly lighter than the colour of the surrounding veins;

(1) vein partly spectral (not counting the last 10% of the vein);

(2) vein through whole length spectral (+-);

(3) absent (not counting the first and last 10% of the vein, even though they can be tubular).

#180. Hind wing, last abscissa of CU (2CU), sclerotization:

(0) vein tubular through the whole length (not counting the last 10% of the vein), same colour as or slightly lighter than the colour of the surrounding veins;

(1) vein partly spectral (not counting the last 10% of the vein);

(2) vein through whole length spectral (+-);

(3) absent.

#181. Hind wing, last abscissa of M (**2M**), **presence**:

- (0) absent;
- (1) present.

#182. Hind wing, ratio of **1Rs to rs-m** [ordered]:

Write ratio.

#183. Hind wing, **ratio of 1M to rs-m** [ordered]:

Write ratio.

#184. Hind wing, **basal hamuli, location**:

- (0) some distance from wing base, on membrane or on spectral vein;
- (1) close to wing base, on spur of tubular vein;
- (2) absent, though in their place often with slightly thickened hairs;
- (3) very large number of basal (!) hamuli along entire margin, half grown over by a more sclerotized narrow wing membrane in front of Sc + R (Hybrizontinae).

#185. Hind wing, **basal hamuli, number** [ordered]:

- (0) one;
- (1) two;
- (2) three;
- (3) four;
- (4) eight.

#186. Hind wing, **distal hamuli, number**:

Write number

#187. Hind wing, distal hamuli, **position**, relative to base of R1 vein:

- (0) **first hamulus closer to the second** one than to the base of R1 vein (Fig.x);
- (1) **first hamulus closer to the base of R1** or at least as distant to base of R1 as to the second hamulus.

#188. Hind wing, distal hamuli, **distribution**:

- (0) **equally inter-spaced**;
- (1) forming groups, with distance between hamuli inside a group clearly shorter than distance between groups. Sometimes, the basal group is represented by only one isolated hamulus.

#####

Main colours

#####

#189. Mesosoma and metasoma, **main colour** ("ground plan colour"):

- (0) black or brown (also when metasoma dark, while mesosoma partly or mostly yellow/orange);
- (1) orange;

(2) yellow.

#190. Face, sexual dimorphism, **main colour**:

- (0) same as ground plan colour in both sexes;
- (1) same as ground plan colour in female, male with different colour;
- (2) same as ground plan colour in male, female with different colour;
- (3) different than ground plan colour in both sexes.

#####

Metasoma

#191. Metasoma, **shape**:

- (0) **depressed** to cylindrical all the way;
- (1) **compressed** from **segment 5**;
- (2) compressed from **segment 4**;
- (3) compressed from **segment 3**.

#####

First tergite - T1

#####

#192. Tergite 1, **dorso-lateral longitudinal carina**:

- (0) more or less complete, above spiracle;
- (1) more or less complete, below or at spiracle;
- (2) more or less absent, at most a vestige anteriorly and/or posteriorly;
- (3) more or less complete but far below spiracle, posteriorly abruptly curved upwards.

#193. Tergite 1, **glymma** [ordered]:

- (0) absent;
- (1) present, but rather **shallow**, not meeting at midline (although each glymma may join lateral sides of anterodorsal sulcus of T1) (cf. *Phytodietus*);
- (2) very **deep**, compared to its height (cf. *Netelia*).

(1) *Phytodietus* sp.

(2) *Rasnichneumon gracilis*

#194. Tergite 1, apically, **fusion of sternite 1**:

- (0) **not fused** to T1 (cf. *Rhyssa*);
- (1) **fused**, but suture visible (cf. *Megarhyssa*);
- (2) **fused**, no suture visible.

#195. Tergite 1, dorsal view, **dimension** [ordered]:

- (0) subquadrate;

- (1) elongate, from about 1.5–3.5 times as long as posteriorly wide;
- (2) very long and slender, >4.0 times as long as posteriorly broad.

#196. Tergite 1, dorsal view, **shape**:

- (0) **petiolate**, clear separation of postpetiolus;
- (1) **parallel** sided (box-like);
- (2) evenly **tapering** to front.

#197. Tergite 1, lateral view, **shape**:

- (0) **rounded basally** or with a **hump around mid length**, thus in profile narrower in the front than in the apical half;
- (1) **flat**, at most with a very weak rounding basally, thus of **even thickness**;
- (2) **basally straight** and sometimes **continuously expanding**, and with an **angle in second half** (often when petiolate).

(0) *Exochus* sp.

(2) *Coelichneumon biannulatus*

#198. Tergite 1, **constriction**:

- (0) no diagonal constriction around mid length of tergite;
- (1) with a constriction showing as a diagonal groove on the sides becoming a transverse impression dorsally (cf. *Xorides*).

#199. Tergite 1, **separation to Tergite 2**:

- (0) separated by a **normal joint**, thus as flexible as T2 to T3;
- (1) partially **fused** so that T2 cannot move independently (cf. *Metopius*).

#200. Tergite 1, **latero-median carinae**, length [ordered]:

- (0) absent;
- (1) less than half length of tergite;
- (2) more than half length of tergite.

#201. Tergite 1, **latero-median carinae**, position:

- NA absent or too short to tell
- (0) **converging**, but then still about as far apart as distance to lateral margin;
- (1) very **strongly converging**, ending up very close together when they become parallel;

(2) just **parallel**, (on elongate T1).

#202. Tergite 1, lateral view, **spiracle**, position [ordered]:

Measurement: T1 length to spiracle (1)/ T1 complete length (2)

#203. Tergite 1, **dorsal surface** in the posterior half, **dominant sculpture**:

- (0) **smooth** and impunctate;
- (1) **finely punctate**, punctures small and distant;
- (2) very **coarsely punctate**, with punctures separated by about their own diameter;
- (3) **coarsely and closely punctate**, the punctures more or less contiguous (no rugae);
- (4) **shagreened**;
- (5) with **sharp transverse rugae** more or less punctured inbetween;
- (6) with longitudinal **parallel**, more or less **dense** rugae and indistinct punctures;
- (7) **rugopunctured** (rugae more or less longitudinal, interrupted, with punctures);
- (8) **shagreened** and **longitudinal rugae**.

(0) *Poecilocryptus nigromaculatus*

(3) *Ichneumon* sp.

(4) *Lorio* sp.

(6) *Gelis* sp.

(7) *Diplazon laetatorius*

#204. Tergite 1, **laterotergite**:

- (0) more or less **absent, very short**;
- (1) **broad** on almost entire length of tergite and membranous;
- (2) **short and triangular** but, with at least some colour (cf. Orthocentrinae: Dialipsis);
- (3) **elongate triangular** with some colour;
- (4) **triangular** on almost **entire length** and membranous.

#####

First sternite - S1

#####

#205. Sternite 1, **length compared to T1** [ordered]:

- (0) very short, <0.3;
- (1) about 0.4–0.5 of length of tergite;
- (2) very long, >0.6 - 0.9;
- (3) almost till the end of tergite

#206. Sternite 1, **shape**:

- (0) with a weak to strong median keel anteriorly;
- (1) flat, without a median longitudinal keel;
- (2) with a median anterior invagination;
- (3) as 0 but with additionally transversal carinae behind

#207. Sternite 1, **central ornamentation**:

- (0) absent;
- (1) present.

#208. Sternite 1, **central ornamentation, modification**:

- NA if absent
- (0) longitudinal swelling on almost whole of the S1 length;
- (1) with a low **rounded swelling**;
- (2) with a **strong sharp transverse crest**;
- (3) with a **pointed tubercle**;

- (4) with **paired tubercles**;
- (5) with **large swelling**;
- (6) with a **low round swelling** and longitudinal crest (*Allomacrus*);
- (7) with **paired round swellings**;
- (8) with a **strong protruding longitudinal swelling** (*Hyperacmus*).

#####

Second tergite - T2

#209. Tergite 2, dorsal view, **length** [ordered]:

[Measurement: Length at midline / width at **base**]

- (0) transverse to subquadrate;
- (1) 1.3–2.5 times as long as posteriorly broad;
- (2) >2.5 times as long as posteriorly broad.

#210. Tergite 2, lateral, **length compared to Tergite 1** [ordered]:

Measurement: laterally Tergite 1 / laterally Tergite 2

#211. Tergite 2, **latero-median carinae**:

- (0) absent;
- (1) present as two parallel carinae;
- (2) present, fused in a single medial carina.

#212. Tergite 2, **thyridium, presence**:

- (0) absent;
- (1) present.

#213. Tergite 2, thyridium and gastrocoelus, location:

NA if thyridium absent;

- (0) thyridium present, but **not sunken** in gastrocoelus;
- (1) with **deep transverse depression** ('gastrocoelus') in which is the thyridium (Figs 67);
- (2) thyridium in **impression surrounded by carinulae**.

(1) (Gauld et al. 2002)

(2) *Ichneumon* sp.

#214. Tergite 2, thyridium, **position**:

- NA thyridium absent
 (0) **less than one length** or diameter distant from anterior edge of T2;
 (1) **more than or equal to one length** or diameter distant from anterior edge of T2.

(1) *Hypomecus quadriannulatus*

#215. Tergite 2, thyridium, **shape**:

- NA thyridium absent
 (0) **ovoid**;
 (1) **transverse**.

#216. T2, thyridium, position relative to longitudinal axis of metasoma:

NA if thyridium absent.

- (0) Longest axis of the thyridium **coincides** with the longitudinal axis of the tergite;
 (1) Longest axis of the thyridium **transverse** to longitudinal axis of the tergite.

#217. Tergite 2, anterior half, **impressions**:

- (0) simple, with **no impression** behind thyridium (Fig. 67);
 (1) with a **shallow or deep, very oblique impression**, starting +/- medially close to base and pointing towards spiracle or slightly basal to it, thus subtending an angle of $>45^\circ$ to longitudinal axis (Fig. 66);
 (2) with a **deep, oblique impression** starting at base of tergite, about halfway between middle and lateral edge of tergite, and pointing a little behind spiracle, subtending an angle of $<40^\circ$ to longitudinal axis (Fig. 65);
 (3) as state 2, but starting very close to middle of base of tergite;
 (4) with a **weak to moderately strong transverse impression**, sometimes with this only present laterally and not meeting on mid-line;
 (5) with both an **oblique (as states 1-3) and a transverse impression (as 4)**, both meeting close to lateral edge of tergite;
 (6) with **oblique impressions starting** a bit remote from base and meeting an equally strong, subapical transverse carina clearly before meeting lateral edge of tergite (cf. *Lycorina*).

(0) (Gauld et al. 2002)

(1) (Gauld et al. 2002)

(2) (Gauld et al. 2002)

#218. Tergite 2, centrally, sculpture:

- (0) smooth and polished, sometimes with a few isolated punctures (Fig. 68);
- (1) evenly **shagreened** and matt;
- (2) with **deep punctures**;
- (3) **transversely** aciculate;
- (4) rugopunctate;
- (5) finely microreticulate;
- (6) with **longitudinal striae** at least in basal part;
- (7) finely evenly punctured.

(2) *Pimpla isidroï* (Gauld et al. 2002)

(6) *Gelis* sp.

#219. Tergite 2 (and usually 3 and 4), posterior 0.2, **change in sculpture:**

- (0) absent, **not sculpturally differentiated** from anterior part of tergite, at most with extreme posterior end of tergite impunctate;
- (1) present, **sculpture differing from rest** of tergite, usually smooth and impunctate.

(1) (Gauld et al. 2002)

#220. Tergite 2, **laterotergite** [ordered]:

- (0) more or less absent;
- (1) **moderately broad**, 0.25–0.4 times as wide as long, and strongly sclerotized;
- (2) **broad**, >0.5 times as wide as long, and membranous.

#221. Tergite 2, laterotergite, **crease:**

- (0) creased and curved mesad under metasoma (Fig. xx *Netelia*);
- (1) not separated by a crease (Fig. xx *Allophrys* sp).

#222. Tergite 2, spiracle, **position on crease:**

- (0) **above** or right at crease;
- (1) clearly **below**.

#####

Other tergites

#####

#223. Tergite 2 and 3, **fusion:**

- (0) separate, with flexion line allowing movement (Fig. 2);
- (1) fused, without a flexion line.

#224. Tergite 3, **surface and impressions:**

- (0) more or less **evenly convex**, without strongly raised areas;
- (1) with conspicuous **lateromedian rounded swellings** (Fig. 71);
- (2) with a **median rhombic raised area** (Fig. 72);
- (3) with a transverse, lozenge-shaped area, bordered by deep grooves, at least posteriorly;

- (4) with **diagonal grooves** starting basally close to the middle and pointing towards posterior corners of tergite, although not always reaching them (cf. Banchinae - Glyptini);
- (5) with **lateromedian round swellings in basal half** and subapical transverse impression, between which there is a basally pointing flat triangle outlined by strong grooves (cf. *Lycorina*);
- (6) transverse impression, this impression with longitudinal ridges (*Neorhacodes*).

(1) (Gauld et al. 2002)

(2) (Gauld et al. 2002)

#225. Tergite 3, basal thyridium, presence:

- (0) absent;
- (1) present.

#226. Tergite 3, latero-median carinae:

- (0) absent;
- (1) present as **two parallel carinae**;
- (2) present, **fused** in a single medial carina.

#227. Tergite 3, laterotergite:

- (0) more or less absent;
- (1) moderately broad, 0.25–0.4 times as wide as long, and strongly sclerotized;
- (2) broad, >0.5 times as wide as long, and membranous.

#228. Tergite 3, laterotergite, crease:

- (0) separated by a crease at least until the spiracle, posterior part can be without the crease and often turned under (Fig. xx);
- (1) not separated by a crease (Fig. xx *Allophrys*).

#229. Tergite 3 and 4, posterolateral corners:

- (0) more or less **rounded** or **right-angled**;
- (1) incised, so **corner is acute**;
- (2) **obliquely truncate**;
- (3) tergites **extended backwards laterally**, so that they are shorter medially (cf. *Phthorima*, *Campocraspedon* in *Diplazontinae*)

#230. Tergite 3 and 4, colour pattern:

- (0) **uniformly colored** or with a very narrow end margin;
- (1) with colour **different only in the last 0.2** of the tergites;
- (2) with colour **different on more than 0.2** of the tergite;
- (3) with pattern in the form of **paired spots or connected spots**.

#231. Tergite 4, laterotergite [ordered]:

NA if **entirely absent**

- (0) more or less absent, i.e., crease very low;
- (1) **moderately broad**, 0.25–0.4 times as wide as long, and strongly sclerotized;
- (2) **broad**, >0.5 times as wide as long, and membranous.

#232. Tergite 4, **laterotergite**, **crease**:

- (0) separated by a crease at least until the spiracle, posterior part can be without the crease and often turned under (Fig. xx);
- (1) not separated by a crease (Fig. xx *Allophrys*).

#233. Sternite 6 (**hypopygium**), laterally, shape, **female**:

- (0) **inconspicuous** or barely visible (e.g. *Pimplini*);
- (1) **square or rectangle**, more conspicuous (e.g. *Campopleginae* and probably most of the other groups with strongly compressed metasoma);
- (2) **more or less triangular** but with **the longest side rounded** (e.g. *Clistopyga*);
- (3) **equilateral triangle** or if scalene triangle, then the longest side straight (e.g. *Mesochorinae*);
- (4) **triangular** with upper side **sinuous**, medially membranous (e.g. *Lycorina*);
- (5) **strongly triangular** (e.g. *Acaenitinae*);
- (6) **oval shape**, about equal thickness throughout.

(0) *Epitheronia*

(2) *Clistopyga incitator*

(3) *Cidaphus atricilla*

(6) *Neotypus melanocephalus*

#234. Sternite 6 (**hypopygium**), **length** [ordered]:

- (0) shortened, not protruding after posterior end of metasoma;
- (1) reaching to posterior end of metasoma;

- (2) clearly protruding after posterior end of metasoma (protruding from posterior end of metasoma by at least median height of S6);
- (3) very elongated, by more than 2x S6 median height.

(0) *Epitheronia*

(2) *Neotypus melanocephalus*

#235. Sternite 6 (hypopygium), posterior margin, ventral view, **median notch**:

NA if absent

- (0) not reaching back to half of S6 length (cut), (e.g. Banchinae);
- (1) almost on **entire length** of S6 (e.g. Acaenitinae, *Pseudorhyssa*).

#236. Tergite 7, **size**, compared to tergite 6, **female** [ordered]:

- (0) conspicuously **shorter** (at most 0.6x as long as tergite 6);
- (1) **similar** in size, sometimes partially retracted under it, but not very noticeably smaller;
- (2) conspicuously **longer**.

#237. Tergite 7, **size**, compared to tergite 6, **male** [ordered]:

- (0) conspicuously **shorter** (at most 0.6x as long as tergite VI), or retracted invisible;
- (1) **similar** size to or slightly smaller than tergite 6;
- (2) **longer** and usually more strongly sclerotized than tergite 6.

#238. Anterior sternites of female (usually at least S2-S4):

- (0) without ovipositor guides;
- (1) with tubercular ovipositor guides (*Megarhyssa*).

#239. Tergite 8, **size and shape**, **female**:

- (0) short;
- (1) elongate dorsally, but not forming a horn or boss (*Odontocolon albotibial*);
- (2) elongate dorsally into a horn or boss (Fig. xx *Megarhyssa g. greenei*);
- (3) laterally elongate, dorsally with a hole through which T9 is visible (see *Xenoschesis*, Ctenopelmatinae);
- (4) T8 very short along mid-line, lateral portions expanding further backwards.

#240. Sternite 8, **shape**, **male**:

- (0) more or less **transverse** and moderately sclerotized (Fig. 78);
- (1) **strongly sclerotized, short, deeply convex**, closing apex of metasoma at rest (Figs 79, 80);
- (2) **weakly to moderately sclerotized and rather flat, but elongate**, more or less closing apex of metasoma at rest (Figs 81, 82);

- (3) similar to (0), but **with a median emargination** (very small one, so maybe it should go to 0);
- (4) narrow, **paddle-shaped** (cf. some Diplazontinae);
- (5) **strongly and evenly concave posteriorly**.

(0) (Gauld et al. 2002)

(1) (Gauld et al. 2002)

(1) (Gauld et al. 2002)

(2) (Gauld et al. 2002)

(2) (Gauld et al. 2002)

#241. Tergite 9, division in male:

- (0) entire;
- (1) medially longitudinally divided.

#242. T8-T9, separation from between tergites in male:

- (0) laterally separated, with tergite VIII forming a lateral plate on the side of tergite IX (Fig. 99, Gauld et al. 2002);
- (1) with tergites VIII and IX completely fused laterally, seemingly just a single tergite (Figs 100, 101).

(Gauld et al. 2002)

#243. Tergite 9, division in **female**:

- (0) from triangular to strap-like, immutably fused with preceding tergite (though the join is generally discernible because of differing sculpture patterns) and occupying an indentation in it;
- (1) almost D-shaped, and positioned behind (rather than within) T8, the joint between the two very weakly sclerotized;
- (2) separated (some outgroup);
- (3) forming a cornus (some outgroups);
- (4) within the cavity of T8 (cf. *Xenoschesis*).

#####

Male genitalia

#244. Aedeagus, **apex**:

- (0) subcylindrical;
- (1) dorsoventrally depressed.

#245. Parameres, **size**, male:

- (0) about 1-2x as long as wide at mid length;
- (1) **strongly elongate**, apically rod-like (cf. *Mesochorus*);
- (2) **short**, inconspicuous;
- (3) **enlarged**, around 0.5x as deep as metasoma at deepest point (*Agriotypus armatus*).

(1) *Lepidura collaris*

#####

Ovipositor

#246. Ovipositor **sheath, setae, position**:

- (0) evenly distributed;
- (1) hairs becoming more sparse in apical third;
- (2) only hairs are along the inner lower margin;
- (3) only some long sparse hairs on apical half;
- (4) evenly distributed, but with a dense cluster of hairs at apical tip.

#247. Ovipositor **sheath, setae, length** [ordered]:

- (0) short (longest setae clearly shorter than the width of ovipositor sheath);
- (1) normal dimension (length about same as sheath width, +/- 10%);
- (2) long (longest setae clearly exceeding width of sheath).

#248. Ovipositor **sheath, setae, density** [ordered]:

- (0) nearly no setae;
- (1) sparse (setae separated by several times their diameter);
- (2) dense.

#249. Ovipositor **sheath, shape**:

NA if shorter than height of metasoma, thus hard to tell;

- (0) more or less parallel sided, sometimes continuously enlarged towards apex or clearly enlarged at tip (cf. Apechthis);
- (1) distinctly enlarged around middle, more narrow before and after (cf. Thymaris, Zagryphus etc. in Tryphoninae);
- (2) evenly narrowed at least on posterior half;
- (3) broad until close to the end, then narrowed, along most of the length with lower part thickened to narrow the interior channel (seen on the inside of the sheaths - cf. Astiphromma);
- (4) very broad, as wide as long (*Oxytorus*).

#250. Ovipositor sheath, **transversal striations** on basal half:

- (0) absent;
- (1) present.

#251. Ovipositor, sheath, **length** compared to metasoma length [ordered]:

Ratio: Ovipositor sheaths to metasoma length.

#252. Ovipositor, lateral view, **shape**:

- (0) **parallel** sided;
- (1) evenly **tapered**;
- (2) evenly **tapered with enlarged submedian region** of lower valve (Fig. 76);
- (3) **lower valve widened twice**, in front and after notch in dorsal valve (Diplazontinae);
- (4) **slender and needle like** (Wahl Fig. 1-33 Astiphromma).

(2) *Zatyptota petronae* (Gauld et al. 2002)

#253. Ovipositor, tip, **shape**:

- (0) more or less straight;
- (1) up-curved;
- (2) bowed downwards along at least posterior half;
- (3) sinuous;
- (4) abruptly decurved only close to the apex;
- (5) lanceolat shape;
- (6) sinuate (*Picardiella*);
- (7) dorsally thick, abruptly narrow after notch, tip then min. half the width then before the notch (some Anomaloninae).

(3) *Acerataspis* sp.

(6) *Picardiella*

#254. Ovipositor, ventrally, **base**:

- (0) simple;
- (1) **swollen**.

(1) (Gauld et al. 2002)

#255. Ovipositor, **sculpture**:

- (0) **smooth**, apparently unsculptured;
- (1) **matte**;
- (2) at least lower valve weakly to strongly **wrinkled**.

#256. Ovipositor, **transection** [ordered]:

- (0) strongly compressed (Fig. 74);
- (1) subcylindrical, or weakly compressed (Fig. 73);
- (2) depressed.

(0) (Gauld et al. 2002)

(1) (Gauld et al. 2002)

#257. Ovipositor, apical region, **flexibility**:

- (0) rigid;
- (1) capable of being deformed so extreme apex is deflected downwards.

#258. Ovipositor, lower valves, apex, **teeth**:

- (0) with distinctly oblique moderately interspaced teeth; (Fig. 73)
- (1) without discernible teeth;
- (2) with moderately interspaced teeth (except the most proximal one or two) vertical; (Fig. 74)
- (3) with fine file-like teeth.

(0) (Gauld et al. 2002)

(2) (Gauld et al. 2002)

(3) Labeninae, Certonotus sp.

#259. Ovipositor, lower valve, **basal tooth, shape**:

NA if no teeth visible on lower valve;

- (0) basal tooth unspecialized, similar to following teeth;
- (1) basal tooth **enlarged** and **forming a barb**.

#260. Ovipositor, lower valves, basal to apex, **scabrous areas**:

- (0) without discrete scabrous areas;
- (1) with one or more small scabrous areas.

#261. Ovipositor, lower valve, **lobe**:

- (0) not enclosing the upper (Figs 73, 74);

- (1) with a clear lobe partially enclosing upper valve (Fig. 75);
- (2) apically entirely enclosing the upper.

(0) (Gauld et al. 2002)

(1) (Gauld et al. 2002)

(2) Labeninae, *Certonotus* sp.

#262. Ovipositor, lower valves, sclerotization:

- (0) evenly sclerotized;
- (1) with weakly sclerotized area (e.g. Oedemopsini).

#263. Ovipositor, dorsal valve, apex, notch:

- (0) absent;
- (1) weak notch;
- (2) clear notch (Photo: *Absyrtus vicinator*).

#264. Ovipositor, dorsal valve, apex, **modification**:

- (0) smooth, simply tapered, with or without nodus;
- (1) with lateral row of **small denticles**;
- (2) with a **dorsal row of low teeth**;
- (3) weakly sclerotized (*Euceros*);
- (4) **expanded laterally just before the notch**;
- (5) with **two high teeth/nodi** (*Certonotus*);
- (6) with **two tubercles** (*Xorides*);
- (7) conspicuously enlarged at tip, then abruptly ending (cf. Townesitinae).

(2) *Augerella achterbergi* (#2368)

(4) *Aphanistes bellicosus*

References (Pictures)

Gauld I.D., Wahl D.B., Broad G.R. 2002. The suprageneric groups of the Pimplinae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae): a cladistic reevaluation and evolutionary biological study. *Zool. J. Linn. Soc.* 136:421–485.